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● Erratum for Volume 1 (October 2024–December 2025)

The following errors require correction:

- 1 Issue 6, on page 35, English Citation and Chinese Citation: “twenty-five” should be changed to “twenty-four”, “二十五” should be changed to “二十四”;
- 2 Issue 15, on page 121, English Title and English Citation: “Motschulsky” should be changed to “Planet”;
- 3 Issue 17, on page 137, ORCID of Zhuo-Heng JIANG: “0009-0004-1814-6806” should be changed to “0000-0001-9161-4400”;
- 4 Issue 39, on page 388, Introduction, Paragraph 3, Line 1 and Taxonomy, Genus Subtitle: “Gestro, 1899” should be changed to “Gestro, 1898”;
- 5 Issue 39, on page 396, References: “Ballerio & Bezděk 2016:” should be changed to “Ballerio A & Bezděk A 2016:”;
- 6 Issue 59, on page 551, Chinese Citation: “*Probolomyrmex*” should be in italics;
- 7 Issue 61, on page 567, English Title: “stage” should be changed to “stag”;
- 8 Issue 63, on page 593, Abstract: “*Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama (1908)” should be changed to “*Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama, 1908”;
- 9 Issue 63, on page 594, Introduction, Paragraph 3, Line 1: “*Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama (1908)” should be changed to “*Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama, 1908”;
- 10 Issue 67, on page 639, Author’s Surname under the Title: “Yang” should be changed to “YANG”;
- 11 Issue 77, on page 773, English Citation: “Nymphalidae. *The*” should be changed to “Nymphalidae). *The*”;
- 12 Issue 83, on page 829, English Citation: “Nymphalidae. *The*” should be changed to “Nymphalidae). *The*”;
- 13 Issue 98, on page 995, English Citation: “Rutelinae. *The*” should be changed to “Rutelinae). *The*”;
- 14 Issue 99, on page 1035, Figure Caption: “**FIGURE 3.** Body parts of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* **sp. nov.**: **A** anterior view of head **B** anterior view of right proleg **C** dorsal view of right middle leg **D** anterior view of left middle leg **E** dorsal view of right hind leg **F** anterior view of left hind leg (holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).” should be changed to “**FIGURE 3.** Thorax and hind femur of *Simulatacalles yuexiuensis* **sp. nov.**: **A-C** pronotum **D** mesosternum and metasternum **E** metepisternal sutures **F** apex of hind femur, anterior view (**A, C** paratypes, female, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China **B, D-F** holotype, male, Yuexiu, Guangdong, China).”;
- 15 Issue 100, on page 1051, TABLE 1: Both “Southeast China” should be changed to “Northeast China”.

